

Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal

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Abstract:

All businesses are suffering today. One industry that is especially visible and emblematic of our economic struggles is restaurants. In Bacolod City, Food Stalls are patronized by the customers because of its different uniqueness. This study aimed to determine the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal at 888 Chinatown Square and Premier Mall Food Courts, Bacolod City, and formulate possible marketing plan to address concerns and provide enhancement programs to increase sales of food stalls. This study used the descriptive research design and a survey questionnaire was constructed to gather the data from 48 respondents. The degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal according to product shows "high degree" while on the area of price and place shows "moderate degree". The degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables in terms of the given areas shows moderate to high degree of results. Also results shows significant result in the age variable in terms of the area of product, no significant results among those variables in terms of price while there is a significant result in the variable of classification of business in the area of place. With the given result, this paper calls for stall owners to administer training on food quality control; product branding, and a seminar on product innovation.

Keywords: Challenges, food stall, new normal, product, place, promotion

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Food Stall is a temporary structure used to prepare and sell food to the general public (Graset, 2018). In many parts of the world, particularly in the developing countries, food stalls or street food vending also makes an important contribution to employment, household revenue and food security (Habib, 2016). Food safety is a fundamental public health concern that is dependent on various factors such as changing global food production patterns, public expectations, and international trade policies (Rustia et al., 2019). The COVID-19 pandemic has forced the closure of many businesses and establishments including restaurant and catering services (Peñarubia, 2020). It has had a major impact on most food businesses. Some are thriving, some are in lockdown and others are making significant changes to the way in which they reach customers in order to continue trading. In almost all cases, businesses have to adopt new ways of working in order to manage both existing and COVID-19 related risks (Edmunds, 2020). Even though COVID-19 is one of the hardest challenges that the society and companies have faced in recent times (Bajaj, 2020), there is a silver lining in the midst of the crisis situation.

All businesses are suffering today. One industry that is especially visible and emblematic of our economic struggles is restaurants. In Bacolod City, Food Stalls are patronized by the customers because of its different uniqueness. From the variety of food and drinks it offers, it really comes out as a "click" to the public. As observed by the researcher, food and eating has been the primary outlet of people to divert from stress in this new normal. Stalls are usually available anywhere, and you can make it available even in online food booking services. The food offered is budget-friendly, making products available for everybody. With the reason stated above, the researcher is inspired to conduct this study to determine the challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal at Bacolod City that will be used as basis for an intervention plan.

Current State of Knowledge

The dramatic no-show of consumers from the 'center of store' aisle products also demonstrates that consumers prefer to stay away from packaged goods, which is why brainstorming strategies to combat the increasing demand for organic products is one of the major challenges faced by food and beverage managers today. Traceability is one

of the pivotal challenges in food and beverage industry, not just for record management but also to fulfill the bottom line – generating revenue for every sector. An online presence is one of the major challenges of food and beverage industry, considering that consumers are more tech-savvy and socially informed, thanks to the Internet. Undeniably, the challenges faced by food and beverage managers are dime a dozen, owing to the ridiculously fierce competition and the fact that a single change is bound to affect the entire supply chain (Iyer, 2020).

The lockdown experience has impacted everyone in many ways. For some it was an easy transition into the safety of their own bubble, yet for others – an uncertain proposition. Transitioning back to the 'new normal' has certainly come with some real challenges (Nestle, 2020). The food industry has, of course, found it particularly tough. The combination of having to cope with increased demand, paired with restrictions on manufacturing and regulation processes has made life very difficult for everybody in the supply chain (Minchin, 2020).

Food should be placed in clean, disposable containers, which are suitable for food use. To adhere to the rules of social distancing, drivers should drop off the food on the customer's doorstep, and step back while the customer retrieves the food. Delivery bags should be cleaned and disinfected at the beginning of each day and throughout the day. Employers need to ensure their drivers are insured for business use, have a valid driver's licence, MOT and the correct tax for the vehicle, and that the rules on drivers' hours are followed, which have been temporarily relaxed by the government at this time (Salmon, 2020)

Local food producers must brace for a new challenge after lockdowns are lifted in the country: slower and lower food demand, industry players and experts told the Business Mirror. Philippine Institute for Development Studies (PIDS) senior research fellow Roehlano M. Briones said even if food remains essential, demand for these products would still take a blow as Filipinos try to survive the impact of Covid-19. Briones added that Filipinos may opt to repay debts or even borrow more to recoup exhausted savings to survive post-enhanced community quarantine (ECQ). Briones said the implementation of health safety measures like social distancing in the food-service sector, such as restaurants, as part of the "new normal" would result in lower customer capacity, hence, lesser food demand. Briones added that Filipinos may opt to repay debts or even borrow more to recoup exhausted savings to survive post-enhanced community quarantine (ECQ) (Arcalas, 2020).

In recent years many restaurants opted to add new revenue streams like hosting live events or providing co-working spaces. With these ideas off the table, for now, you'll see owners returning to many classic approaches as well. For example, restaurateurs look to regain consumer confidence by avoiding overly promotional marketing campaigns. Instead, they'll focus on boosting customer loyalty and sharing social proof that showcases guests social distancing (Bolanos, 2020). The restaurant industry faced unforeseen challenges across the globe, and I can't over-emphasize the resilience and tenacity required of us to persevere in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic. Restaurants are working hard to adopt measures to protect their customers, but safeguarding employees is an equally important – if not somewhat greater – challenge (Chemero, 2021).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is connected on the theory of business challenges by Ries (2011). As Ries stated, entrepreneurs face a different set of challenges because they operate with much higher uncertainty. There are many different views of encounter the business challenges and options of strategy implementation. Business challenges can be a trigger in generating brilliant ideas and recognize opportunities into a business. An ability to overcome business challenges can be one of factor of business success.

Business challenges can be considered as a barrier, but in a positive perspective way the business challenge is considered as an opportunity, which must be addressed in conviction that the action taken is appropriate action in creating and developing a business. Many challenging issues in running a business, since business creation such as actualize ideas, venture capital, market identification, legal issues; until business development such as operational management, product development, customer satisfaction and still many other things. Challenge is an important issue for a business; it is beneficial to know what action is needed to make the challenge into an opportunity. Though the business challenges are unique to every business, many of others experiences have the same kinds of challenges. This is what can be used as valuable lessons and references in act from those who have been through it. The theory supports the study of the researcher to outline several ways to measure degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal. This theory is suitable in this study, since it aims to measure the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in terms of the aforementioned areas perceived by the research to adjust to the new normal. This theory will serve as a basis for the researcher to measure the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in Bacolod City.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal at 888 Chinatown Square and Premier Mall Food Courts, Bacolod City during the last three (3) quarters of 2020 as

basis for a marketing plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal according to product, price, place, and promotion; 2) the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables; and 3) the significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedure for data analysis.

Research Design

Considering the nature of the data involved, descriptive research design was used in this study. Descriptive research is valuable in providing facts in which scientific judgment may be based, providing essential knowledge about the nature of objects and persons and for closer observation into the practices, behavior, methods, and procedures, and playing a large part in the development of instruments for the measurement of many gathering instruments like questionnaires, tests, interviews, checklists, score cards, rating scales, and observation schedules, and formulating of policies in the local, national, or international level (Calmorin, 2016). Descriptive research design is valuable to this present study in providing facts and scientific judgement based on assessing this study. Also, this design is appropriate for the study as to know the present situation and to determine the prevailing issues making adequate and accurate interpretation of the data.

Study Respondents

A total of 48 food stall owners were the respondents of the study. These respondents are the Food Stall Owners inside the Chinatown 888 Mall, Bacolod City. Due to a small number of populations, the researcher decided to include all the identified respondents. No sampling technique was utilized.

Instruments

A researcher-made survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data to determine the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal for the Calendar Year 2020-2021. It was subjected to validity (3.63-very good) and reliability (0.969-excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. The questionnaire was divided into two parts wherein part I deals with the profile of respondents in terms of age, classification of business, average daily gross sales, and type of product. Part II of the questionnaire is a 27-item statement for the areas, 8 for Product, 8 for Price, and 8 for Place, which measures the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal using 5-point Likert scale rating with 5 as always, 4 as often, 3 as sometimes, 2 as rarely and 1 as almost never.

Data Gathering Procedure

After establishing the validity and reliability of the instrument, the researcher wrote a letter to the Manager of 888 Chinatown Square and Premier Mall Food Courts, Bacolod City to ask permission for the conduct of the study. Upon approval, the researcher set a schedule for the data gathering with a letter of request to the Food Stall Owners in the said company. In the conduct, the researcher explained the purpose of the study, personally administered the questionnaire to the respondents to guide them carefully in answering and giving the needed data, and retrieve the questionnaires. The respondents were assured of the confidentiality of the data gathered. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used in the processing of the encoded data.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1, used descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal according to the areas, product, price, and place.

Objective No. 2, used descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal when they are grouped according to the variables, age, classification of business, average daily gross sales, and type of product.

Objective No. 3, used comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test to determine whether or not a significant difference exist in the degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal when they are grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Research Ethics Protocols are a set of principles that guide your research designs and practices. These principles include voluntary participation, informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, and risk of harm (Bhandari, 2021). All research respondents are free to choose to participate without any pressure or coercion, and they understand all the information they need to decide whether they want to participate. Ethical standards require that researchers not put participants in a situation where they might be at risk of harm because of their participation. The researcher also guarantees the participants' confidentiality, and they are assured that identifying information will not be made available to anyone not directly involved in the study. The researcher will use an alternative method of identifying information in this study.

Results and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain appropriate procedures so as to give the exact data and solution to each specific problem.

Table 1
 Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Product

Items	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?		
1. Variety of products offered in menu	3.46	Moderate Degree
2. Shelf life of the food products offered	3.52	High Degree
3. Availability of product suppliers'	3.27	Moderate Degree
4. Labelling and description of product	3.46	Moderate Degree
5. Nutritional value of the products	3.65	High Degree
6. Product serving size/portion	3.46	Moderate Degree
7. Packaging material and product presentation	3.52	High Degree
8. Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture	3.67	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.50	High Degree

Table 1 on the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal showed that item 8 "Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture." obtained the highest mean of 3.67 interpreted as "high degree". This implies that most respondents are focused more on the quality of their products. Customers are usually looking for a food product based on their primary bases: taste, color and texture. They will buy and eat what is good in palate and palatable to look at. It's a must for a food seller to make their product presentable in all aspects. The result of the study confirms the findings of Wolgast, H., Halverson, M. M., Kennedy, N., Gallard, I., & Karpyn, A. (2022), which shows that consumers are looking for what they deem to be healthier products, and packaged foods companies have seen sales dip as consumers hug the outer rim of grocery stores rather than buying more of their products from center store shelves. Perimeter means fresh, natural, and whole foods while center of store foods are thought to be more processed. On the contrary, item 3 "Availability of products suppliers.'" got the lowest mean of 3.27 interpreted as "moderate degree". This means that respondents have least challenge when it comes to supplies of products. Respondents have numerous suppliers of the resources they need for the production. This is true when Teng, (2020), recommended to shorten the supply chains; formulate/implement policies to avoid export restrictions; and increase production/productivity of existing farms, self-production, and support for locally produced food. Moreover, the overall mean score is 3.50, which showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of product was "high degree".

Table 2
 Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Price

Items	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?		
1. Overall value of the product for income	3.19	Moderate Degree
2. Competitor's prices	3.27	Moderate Degree
3. Potential substitute products from competitors	3.31	Moderate Degree
4. Product bundles	3.15	Moderate Degree
5. Multiple payment options	3.04	Moderate Degree
6. Free or complimentary items	2.96	Moderate Degree
7. Price sensitivity of consumers	3.15	Moderate Degree
8. Consumers' purchasing power	3.23	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.16	Moderate Degree

Table 2 on the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal revealed the highest mean of 3.31, interpreted with "moderate degree" on item 3 "Potential substitute products from competitors." This means that most respondents is challenged with their competitor having similar products from

what they offer to the market. Small food businesses usually face problems in competitions within the market towards the products they offer. The result was more likely conform by Iyer, (2020), the challenges faced by food and beverage managers are dime a dozen, owing to the ridiculously fierce competition and the fact that a single change is bound to affect the entire supply chain. On the contrary, item 6 "Free or complimentary items." got the lowest mean of 2.96, interpreted as "moderate degree". This implies that most of the respondents can offer free or complimentary items in order to boost their sales. This is a common strategy between food businesses to attract more clients by adding a freebie to their regular product. According to Tran, (2021), managers need to be innovative in seeking alternative forms of supplies which raise the interest in the facilitation between firms and consumers. Meanwhile, the overall mean score is 3.16; this inferred that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of price was "moderate degree".

Table 3
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Place

Items	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?		
1. Strategic business location	3.29	Moderate Degree
2. Physical store layout	3.23	Moderate Degree
3. Presence of other food stalls in the area.	3.46	Moderate Degree
4. Take-out services offered	3.46	Moderate Degree
5. Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)	3.00	Moderate Degree
6. Dine in seating capacity	3.33	Moderate Degree
7. Service area sanitation practices	3.44	Moderate Degree
8. Waiting area space	3.31	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.32	Moderate Degree

Table 3 on the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal showed that item 3 and 4 "Presence of other food stalls in the area." and "Take-out services offered." obtained the highest mean of 3.46 interpreted as "moderate degree". This implies that most of the respondents is challenged with the close competition within the market. The presence of other food stalls hinders the food businesses to succeed easily in boosting their daily gross sales. And as well, its also a challenge for the food stall owners to offer take-out services for the customers. In this new normal setting, most of the customers preferred to eat at home to avoid the infectious virus threat. Findings is supported by Iyer, (2020), undeniably, the challenges faced by food and beverage managers are dime a dozen, owing to the ridiculously fierce competition and the fact that a single change is bound to affect the entire supply chain. An online presence is one of the major challenges of food and beverage industry, considering that consumers are more tech-savvy and socially informed, thanks to the Internet. On the other hand, item 5 "Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)." got the lowest mean of 3.00 interpreted as "moderate degree". This would imply that most of the respondents have least challenge when it comes to delivery services. Since this is one of the new trends in the food service industry, most of the food businesses also featured this type of service. The convenience provided by different delivery services through online platforms have given the customers the security to avail the food they crave in the comfort of their homes. According to Salmon, (2020), to adhere to the rules of social distancing, drivers should drop off the food on the customer's doorstep, and step back while the customer retrieves the food. Delivery bags should be cleaned and disinfected at the beginning of each day and throughout the day. Employers need to ensure their drivers are insured for business use, have a valid driver's license, MOT and the correct tax for the vehicle, and that the rules on drivers' hours are followed, which have been temporarily relaxed by the government at this time (Salmon, 2020) Moreover, the overall mean score is 3.32, which showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of place was "moderate degree".

Table 4
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Product when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Variety of products offered in menu	3.81	High Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
2. Shelf life of the food products offered	3.78	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
3. Availability of product suppliers'	3.70	High Degree	2.71	Moderate Degree
4. Labelling and description of product	3.78	High Degree	3.05	Moderate Degree
5. Nutritional value of the products	3.96	High Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree
6. Product serving size/portion	3.74	High Degree	3.10	Moderate Degree
7. Packaging material and product	3.78	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree

presentation

8. Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture	3.96	High Degree	3.29	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.82	High Degree	3.10	Moderate Degree

Degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal when the respondents are grouped according to Age, revealed that item 5 and 8 "Nutritional value of the products." and "Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture." got the highest mean of 3.96 as assessed by younger respondents interpreted with "high degree". This signifies that most of the younger respondents always consider the nutritional value of the products they offer to the customers. Above all, they value health in all aspects especially in this new normal. At the same time, the good quality of their food products is also considered. A quality food product means a balanced taste, color and texture. Result relates in an article written by Wolgast, H., Halverson, M. M., Kennedy, N., Gallard, I., & Karpyn, A. (2022). that consumers are looking for what they deem to be healthier products, and packaged foods companies have seen sales dip as consumers hug the outer rim of grocery stores rather than buying more of their products from center store shelves. However, item 3 "Availability of product suppliers." obtained the lowest mean of 2.71 interpreted with "moderate degree" as assessed by older respondents. This means that most of the older respondents are not challenged when it comes to the suppliers of their resources for the production. Probably this is because of the easy access and availability of the suppliers. Results conforms in the study of Henry, (2020), that these disruptions are, specifically, the restrictions on people's global movement, delays in the supply of raw materials and import-export transactions, price fluctuations, the lack of workers in agriculture, increased farming costs, and distribution deficiencies (Henry, 2020). As shown in the same table, younger group garnered the overall mean score of 3.82, whereas, older group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 3.10. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of product when grouped according to age was "moderate degree".

Table 5

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Price when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Overall value of the product for income	3.52	High Degree	2.76	Moderate Degree
2. Competitor's prices	3.48	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
3. Potential substitute products from competitors	3.56	High Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
4. Product bundles	3.52	High Degree	2.67	Moderate Degree
5. Multiple payment options	3.26	Moderate Degree	2.76	Moderate Degree
6. Free or complimentary items	3.22	Moderate Degree	2.62	Moderate Degree
7. Price sensitivity of consumers	3.26	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
8. Consumers' purchasing power	3.41	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.41	Moderate Degree	2.85	Moderate Degree

As shown in Table 5, degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal when the respondents are grouped according to Age, got the highest mean of 3.56 obtained by younger respondents interpreted with "high degree" on item 3 "Potential substitute products from competitors." The result implies that most of the younger respondents is challenged with the presence of competitors with similar products in the market. Potential substitute products tighten the competition between food businesses. It may also lower the rate of average daily gross sales. According to Minchin, (2020), the food industry has, of course, found it particularly tough. The combination of having to cope with increased demand, paired with restrictions on manufacturing and regulation processes has made life very difficult for everybody in the supply chain. On the contrary, item 6 "Free or complimentary items." got the lowest mean of 2.62 as obtained by older respondents interpreted as "moderate degree". This means that most of the older respondents is least challenged in giving free or complimentary items to customers. It has been part of their practice to give extra items in order to boost their sales. This supports the study of Tran, (2021), that managers need to be innovative in seeking alternative forms of supplies which raise the interest in the facilitation between firms and consumers. As shown in the same table, younger group garnered the overall mean score of 3.41, whereas, older group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 2.85. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of price when grouped according to age was "moderate degree".

Table 5

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Place when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger	Older
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To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Strategic business location	3.63	High Degree	2.86	Moderate Degree
2. Physical store layout	3.48	Moderate Degree	2.90	Moderate Degree
3. Presence of other food stalls in the area.	3.63	High Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree
4. Take-out services offered	3.81	High Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
5. Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)	3.22	Moderate Degree	2.71	Moderate Degree
6. Dine in seating capacity	3.41	Moderate Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree
7. Service area sanitation practices	3.63	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
8. Waiting area space	3.30	Moderate Degree	3.33	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.52	High Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree

As shown in Table 5, degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal when the respondents are grouped according to Age, got the highest mean of 3.81 obtained by younger respondents interpreted with "high degree" on item 4 "Take-out services offered." This would mean that most of the respondents in younger group is challenged in offering take-out services. They prefer to serve food products on premise rather than off-premise. It may appear inconvenient to food business to prepare food products for take-away and extend business service unit for take-out. According to Salmon, (2020), food businesses must continue to adhere to their legal duties, such as an employer's duty to protect their employees' health and safety and the health and safety of customers, including in relation to food safety and hygiene regulations. At the same time, food businesses must also abide by the government's current restrictions. In contrary, item 5 "Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)" got the lowest mean of 2.71 as obtained by older respondents interpreted as "moderate degree". This further implies that the respondents in older group have least challenges when it comes to delivery services of their food products. They may have extended units for customers who can not avail the products on premise. It's the convenience that the food businesses may offer to reach their customers especially their patrons. Corke, (2015), stated a firm declaration of national policy on food safety and the creation of a single authority mandated with a focused integrated and comprehensive plan of action will ensure the delivery of safe food to consumers in the country. As shown in the same table, younger group garnered the overall mean score of 3.52, whereas, older group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 3.06. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of place when grouped according to age was "high degree".

Table 6

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Product when grouped according to Average Daily Gross Sales

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Variety of products offered in menu	3.42	Moderate Degree	3.53	High Degree
2. Shelf life of the food products offered	3.45	Moderate Degree	3.65	High Degree
3. Availability of product suppliers'	3.19	Moderate Degree	3.41	Moderate Degree
4. Labelling and description of product	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.59	High Degree
5. Nutritional value of the products	3.55	High Degree	3.82	High Degree
6. Product serving size/portion	3.32	Moderate Degree	3.71	High Degree
7. Packaging material and product presentation	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.76	High Degree
8. Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture	3.52	High Degree	3.94	High Degree
Overall Mean	3.41	Moderate Degree	3.68	High Degree

Data presented in Table 6, showed that degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal when the respondents are grouped according to Average Daily Gross Sales, assessment of respondents with higher daily sales on item 5 "Nutritional value of the products." got the highest mean of 3.82 interpreted with "high degree". This indicates that the respondents with higher daily gross sales are challenged when it comes to providing products with nutritional value. In this new normal, customers are looking for food products that will nourish them and keep them healthy. This means that food businesses should also consider serving healthy food products. According to the study of Wolgast, H., Halverson, M. M., Kennedy, N., Gallard, I., & Karpyn, A. (2022).

that consumers are looking for what they deem to be healthier products, and packaged foods companies have seen sales dip as consumers hug the outer rim of grocery stores rather than buying more of their products from center store shelves. Perimeter means fresh, natural, and whole foods while center of store foods are thought to be more processed. However, item 3 "Availability of product suppliers." obtained the lowest mean of 3.19 interpreted with "moderate degree" as assessed by respondents with lower daily sales. This means that most of the respondents with lower daily gross sales is least challenged when it comes to suppliers of their product. They can easily look for suppliers who can give them the resources for their production. Result agreed by Rustia, (2020), challenges in food safety is present throughout the food supply chain and it remains a growing concern globally. Several factors contribute to the increased exposure of populations to more food hazards including but not limited to freer trade and globalization of food products. As shown in the same table, higher daily gross sales group garnered the overall mean score of 3.68, whereas, lower daily gross sales group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 3.41. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of product when grouped according to average daily gross sales was "high degree".

Table 7
 Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Price when grouped according to Average Daily Gross Sales

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Overall value of the product for income	3.10	Moderate Degree	3.35	Moderate Degree
2. Competitor's prices	3.32	Moderate Degree	3.18	Moderate Degree
3. Potential substitute products from competitors	3.35	Moderate Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree
4. Product bundles	3.16	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
5. Multiple payment options	3.10	Moderate Degree	2.94	Moderate Degree
6. Free or complimentary items	2.97	Moderate Degree	2.94	Moderate Degree
7. Price sensitivity of consumers	3.16	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
8. Consumers' purchasing power	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.12	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.18	Moderate Degree	3.13	Moderate Degree

Degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal when the respondents are grouped according to Average Daily Gross Sales showed that the highest mean of 3.35 interpreted with "moderate degree" was obtained by item 1 "Overall value of the product for income." and item 3 "Potential substitute products from competitors." This implies that both respondents with higher and lower daily gross sales is challenged with the overall value of their product in the aspect of income and the competitors having potential similar products in the common market. Business owners need to consider the production cost when it comes to price. And as well, realizing the competition from other food business owners with potential substitute products to what they usually offer. Result agrees with the study of Bolanos, (2020), that Hospitality businesses face unprecedented revenue losses and hope to find a new normal to finish the year off in the black. But, doing so may require some creative thinking, including revamping business models. Restaurant and bar owners step up to meet revenue shortfalls in many unique ways. For instance, many restaurateurs shifted to selling meal kits and offering delivery during the shutdown. Going forward, business owners will continue to diversify their offerings to support lower sales due to social distancing. Likewise, the lowest mean of 2.94 interpreted with "moderate degree" was obtained by item 5 "Multiple payment options." and item 6 "Free or complimentary items.", both assessed by respondents with higher and lower daily gross sales. Finding suggests that both respondents with higher and lower daily gross sales is least challenged when it comes to different payment options and free or complimentary offers for their customers. This means that they can offer multiple modes of payment for the convenience and safety of their clients. They can also give items with free of charge for the purpose of marketing for potential future clients. According to Bolanos, (2020), for now, you'll see owners returning to many classic approaches as well. For example, restaurateurs look to regain consumer confidence by avoiding overly promotional marketing campaigns. Instead, they'll focus on boosting customer loyalty and sharing social proof that showcases guests social distancing. As shown in the same table, lower daily gross sales group garnered the overall mean score of 3.18, whereas, higher daily gross sales group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 3.13. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of price when grouped according to average daily gross sales was "moderate degree".

Table 8
 Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Place when grouped according to Average Daily Gross Sales

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following				

Areas?	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Strategic business location	3.23	Moderate Degree	3.41	Moderate Degree
2. Physical store layout	3.06	Moderate Degree	3.53	High Degree
3. Presence of other food stalls in the area.	3.39	Moderate Degree	3.59	High Degree
4. Take-out services offered	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.76	High Degree
5. Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)	2.90	Moderate Degree	3.18	Moderate Degree
6. Dine in seating capacity	3.29	Moderate Degree	3.41	Moderate Degree
7. Service area sanitation practices	3.26	Moderate Degree	3.76	High Degree
8. Waiting area space	3.26	Moderate Degree	3.41	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.21	Moderate Degree	3.51	High Degree

As shown in Table 8, Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal when the respondents are grouped according to Average Daily Gross Sales, item 4 "Take-out services offered." and item 7 "Service area sanitation practices." got the highest mean of 3.76 interpreted with "high degree" as assessed by the higher daily gross sales respondents. Finding suggests that most respondents with higher daily gross sales is challenged when they offer food take-out services to customers and in practicing sanitation in the food service area. This means that business owners see it difficult in extending units for food take-out services. They might have a minimal business place. While, there's also a pressure when it comes to sanitation practices in the service area. This is because of the tight guidelines from the government and the establishment. According to Vasquez, (2020), Restaurants and other food providers must also brace for substantial changes resulting from recommended social distancing. Food industry participants must also be extremely vigilant in adopting appropriate and effective disease containment and maintenance policies. On the contrary, item 5 "Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)" got the lowest mean of 3.18 interpreted as "moderate degree" was obtained by lower daily gross sales respondents. This means that respondents with lower daily gross sales have least challenge when it comes to partnership with different delivery services. Business owners may consider them as opportunity that will help the business grows. And in this time of new normal, customers may access these services to avail food products because of the fear of being infected from the threatening virus. According to Bolanos, (2020), for example, guests may not feel comfortable with temperature checks or struggle to stay in their seats after a few cocktails. Reducing restaurant capacity in an industry plagued with low-profit margins isn't easy. Hospitality businesses face unprecedented revenue losses and hope to find a new normal to finish the year off in the black. As shown in the same table, higher daily gross sales group garnered the overall mean score of 3.51, whereas, lower daily gross sales group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 3.21. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of place when grouped according to average daily gross sales was "high degree".

Table 9
Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Product when grouped according to Type of Product

Items	Food		Both Food and Beverages	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Variety of products offered in menu	3.59	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
2. Shelf life of the food products offered	3.66	High Degree	3.25	Moderate Degree
3. Availability of product suppliers'	3.44	Moderate Degree	2.94	Moderate Degree
4. Labelling and description of product	3.66	High Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree
5. Nutritional value of the products	3.75	High Degree	3.44	Moderate Degree
6. Product serving size/portion	3.53	High Degree	3.31	Moderate Degree
7. Packaging material and product presentation	3.66	High Degree	3.25	Moderate Degree
8. Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture	3.78	High Degree	3.44	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.64	High Degree	3.24	Moderate Degree

As shown in Table 9, Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal when the respondents are grouped according to Type of Product, item 8 "Product quality in terms of taste, color and texture." got the highest mean of 3.78 interpreted with "high degree" as assessed by respondents with food product. This means that most of the respondents with food product has greater challenge when it comes to the quality of products in terms of taste, color and texture. New normal setting has affected the quality of food product offered by the businesses. It's always a must for food businesses to produce quality products in order to gain

customers loyalty in return. According to Minchin, (2020), The food industry has, of course, found it particularly tough. The combination of having to cope with increased demand, paired with restrictions on manufacturing and regulation processes has made life very difficult for everybody in the supply chain. On the contrary, item 3 "Availability of product suppliers." got the lowest mean of 2.91 interpreted as moderate degree was obtained by respondents with both food and beverages products. This is to imply that most of the respondents with food and beverage products has a lesser challenge when it comes to availability of product suppliers. Respondents may have ample of partner suppliers to have a smooth business operation. As shown in the same table, respondents with food product group garnered the overall mean score of 3.64, whereas, respondents with non-alcoholic beverages product group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 3.05. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of product when grouped according type of product was "high degree".

Table 9

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Price when grouped according to Type of Product

Items	Food		Both Food and Beverages	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Overall value of the product for income	3.47	Moderate Degree	2.63	Moderate Degree
2. Competitor's prices	3.38	Moderate Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree
3. Potential substitute products from competitors	3.34	Moderate Degree	3.25	Moderate Degree
4. Product bundles	3.25	Moderate Degree	2.94	Moderate Degree
5. Multiple payment options	3.16	Moderate Degree	2.81	Moderate Degree
6. Free or complimentary items	3.03	Moderate Degree	2.81	Moderate Degree
7. Price sensitivity of consumers	3.25	Moderate Degree	2.94	Moderate Degree
8. Consumers' purchasing power	3.38	Moderate Degree	2.94	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderate Degree	2.93	Moderate Degree

Data presented in Table 9, showed that Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal when the respondents are grouped according to Type of Product, assessment of respondents with food product on item 1 "Overall value of the product for income." got the highest mean of 3.47 interpreted with "moderate degree". This indicates that most of the respondents with food product has greater challenge when it comes to the value of their offered products for income. There are lots of reasons to consider why a food business owner can gain or loss profit with the products they are selling. One is competition between other food businesses. Other problems like production costs are considered. This is true when Iyer, (2020), stated that traceability is one of the pivotal challenges in food and beverage industry, not just for record management but also to fulfill the bottom line - generating revenue for every sector. The challenges faced by food and beverage managers are dime a dozen, owing to the ridiculously fierce competition and the fact that a single change is bound to affect the entire supply chain. In contrast, item 1 "Overall value of the product for income.", also obtained the lowest mean of 2.55 interpreted with "moderate degree" as assessed by respondents with both food and beverage product. This also implies that most respondents with food and beverage products is also least challenged with the overall value of their product when it comes to the aspect for income. The progress of the business by having a good income lies in the balance of production cost. Income depends on the production costs that should be balanced with the suggested price per product. Findings is supported by Teng, (2020), that in order to meet the challenges that COVID19 has imposed on the supply side, he recommended to shorten supply chains; formulate/implement policies to avoid export restrictions; and increase production/productivity of existing farms, self-production, support for locally produced food. As shown in the same table, respondents with food product group garnered the overall mean score of 3.28, whereas, respondents with food and beverage product group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 2.94. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of product when grouped according type of product was "moderate degree".

Table 10

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal in the area of Place when grouped according to Type of Product

Items	Food		Both Food and Beverages	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
To what degree do you find difficulties in the following areas?				
1. Strategic business location	3.41	Moderate Degree	3.06	Moderate Degree
2. Physical store layout	3.25	Moderate Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
3. Presence of other food stalls in the area.	3.59	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
4. Take-out services offered	3.59	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
5. Delivery services (Food Panda,	3.31	Moderate Degree	2.38	Low Degree

Grab Food etc.)

6. Dine in seating capacity	3.56	High Degree	2.88	Moderate Degree
7. Service area sanitation practices	3.56	High Degree	3.19	Moderate Degree
8. Waiting area space	3.47	Moderate Degree	3.00	Moderate Degree
Overall Mean	3.47	Moderate Degree	3.01	Moderate Degree

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Food Stall Owners in the New Normal when the respondents are grouped according to Type of Product showed that the highest mean of 3.59 interpreted with "high degree" was obtained by both item 3 "Presence of other food stalls in the area.", and 4 "Take-out services offered." as obtained by respondents with food product. This implies that most respondents with food product is challenged in offering take-out services. Due to current situations in this new normal setting, safe food handling is very important. From the production up to the service outlets, careful and sanitized handling of food is a must. This is true when Iyer, (2020) stated that the dramatic no-show of consumers from the 'center of store' aisle products also demonstrates that consumers prefer to stay away from packaged goods, which is why brainstorming strategies to combat the increasing demand for organic products is one of the major challenges faced by food and beverage managers today. In contrast, the lowest mean of 2.18 interpreted with "low degree" was obtained by item 5 "Delivery services (Food Panda, Grab Food etc.)." as assessed by respondents with both food and beverage product. This further implies that most respondents with food and beverage product have lesser challenge when it comes to partnering with the trendy delivery services today. Most food businesses today offer delivery services because customers prefer to eat at home for their safety. According to Salmon, (2020), to adhere to the rules of social distancing, drivers should drop off the food on the customer's doorstep, and step back while the customer retrieves the food. Delivery bags should be cleaned and disinfected at the beginning of each day and throughout the day. As shown in the same table, respondents with food product group garnered the overall mean score of 3.47, whereas, respondents with food and beverage product group counterparts obtained the overall mean score of 2.96. Results showed that the degree of challenges encountered by food stall owners in the new normal in the area of place when grouped according type of product was "moderate degree".

Conclusions:

The degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal according to product shows "high degree" while on the area of price, and place, shows "moderate degree". The degree of challenges encountered by Food Stall Owners in the new normal when they are grouped according to the aforementioned variables in terms of the given areas shows moderate to high degree of results. Also results shows significant result in the age variable in terms of the area of product, no significant results among those variables in terms of price while there is a significant result in the variable of classification of business in the area of place. With the given result, this paper calls for stall owners to administer training on food quality control; product branding, and a seminar on product innovation.

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